

2. (a) The 2.4-kb product of amplification using PCR from four RTBV strains. (b) The restriction digestion profiles of the 2.4-kb PCR product for the four virus strains using *AccI*, *AluI*, and *EcoRI*.

ethidium bromide and viewing under ultraviolet light (Fig. 2).

To confirm that amplified products were from the virus being studied, Southern blotting was performed using a labeled DNA probe of the 2.4-kb amplified fragment of the reference strain of RTBV and the labeled DNA of the entire reference strain of the virus (data not shown).

Agarose gel electrophoresis did not distinguish the PCR fragments amplified from the four strains (Fig. 2a). Upon digestion with *AccI*, *AluI*, and *EcoRI*, however, variations among the strains were evident (Fig. 2b). Three DNA banding patterns were observed with each of the enzymes used. Strains G₂ and I₂ could not be differentiated by this method.

This information on molecular variation among the four RTBV strains can be used for diagnosis of virus strains. Further studies are needed to determine the molecular basis of the distinct symptoms incited by each strain. ■

Neck blast-resistant lines of Radha-17 isolated

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Rice blast (BI), caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav., is one of the most serious rice diseases in Nepal. Blast can reduce yields by 50% in areas where Masuli, Nepal's most popular variety, is grown.

Masuli and Mallika were crossed to develop Radha-17, which has a yield potential of 4 t/ha and resists leaf BI. Radha-17 was reported to be susceptible to neck BI, another serious disease. We have been working to purify neck BI-resistant lines of Radha-17.

We selected 100 disease-free panicles of Radha-17 grown in farmers' field trials in 1990. Seeds from these panicles were sown at 10-cm spacing in 1-m rows (panicle to row) in 1991. The trial plot was surrounded by two rows of a BI-

susceptible variety and by four rows of *Sesbania aculeata*, which were planted 2 and 4 wk before Radha-17, respectively. The seedbed was inoculated uniformly with 1-yr-old BI-infected rice leaf debris.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 1-m rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing in a field fertilized with 120 kg N/ha and 26.4 kg P/ha. The experiment was inoculated twice at tillering and panicle initiation stages by uniformly spreading chopped pieces of fresh BI-infected leaves. Disease rating was scored at maturity using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

Only 60 of the 100 lines were selected as resistant in 1991. Seeds from these lines were sown in 1992 in single rows with BI-susceptible variety Masuli in alternate rows at 10-cm spacing. All other activities were the same as in 1991.

While Masuli was severely affected by leaf BI at the seedling stage, leaf BI scores in all test lines were less than three on the SES scale. Neck BI scores were 0-5 in 1991 and 0-7 in 1992; 37 lines

were rated as moderately to highly resistant. The other 23 showed susceptible reactions in 1992.

These results suggest that line Radha-17 is not pure with respect to BI resistance. Selection within populations of similar lines might yield BI-resistant materials. ■

Screening rice accessions for resistance to rice tungro

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A severe outbreak of rice tungro (RTD) disease occurred on susceptible varieties ADT36, TKM9, CO 37, IR64, ASD16, and ASD18 in Chengalpattu-MGR District during 1992 sornavari season (Apr/May-Aug/Sep). Disease incidence was 60-85% at RRS. Light trap catches and in situ counts revealed that the vector, green leafhopper (GLH)

Table 1. Incidence of GLH at RRS, Tirur, India. Jul-Sep 1992.^a

Week	Incidence	
	Light trap (no.)	Field (no./25 sweeps)
3 Jul	436	10
10 Jul	1157	30
17 Jul	535	40
24 Jul	1794	110*
31 Jul	1354	330*
7 Aug	7064	920*
14 Aug	86234	150*
21 Aug	13091	40
28 Aug	1192	45
4 Sep	739	15

^a* = above economic threshold level of 60 GLH/25 sweeps.

(*Nephotettix virescens*), was prevalent from Jul to Aug 1992 (Table 1).

Eighty rice entries (69 cultures) and 11 varieties from the 1992 International Irrigated Rice Yield Nursery (early), Advanced Yield Trial (mid-early), and Multilocation Trial III along with susceptible check TN1 were planted in 5-m² plots during the second week of Jul 1992. Plants were infected with RTD at tillering, stem elongation, and booting stages. Reactions varied. Each entry was scored for RTD 45 d after transplanting using the methodology from the 1991 International Rice Tungro Nursery.

The entries and check were screened for their reaction to GLH under screenhouse conditions using the seedbox test. Seedlings were infested with five 2d- and 3d-instar GLH nymphs 7 d after seeding. Entries were scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when 90% of TN1 plants were dead.

None of the entries were resistant to RTD. Twenty-five were moderately resistant (Table 2), 27 moderately susceptible, 19 susceptible, and 9 highly susceptible. ■

Table 2. Rice cultures moderately resistant to RTD. RRS, Tirur, India.

Entry	Parentage	GLH score ^a	RTD (%)	RTD score ^b
IET12888	BR51/KAU2335-2	1	1.7	2
IET12461	IR36/KJT35-3	1	2.2	2
IET12419	IR36/Jothi	1	2.6	2
IR59606-119-3	IR44592-62/IR20289-94	1	2.7	2
IET12488	Ratna/IR36	3	3.2	2
IET12928	IR50/P338	3	4.3	2
IET12867	Palman 579/IR54	3	4.4	2
IET12355	IR50/IR36	3	5.1	3
TNRH6	IR628294/Pusa/50R	3	5.9	3
IET12914	IR50/P33/IR50/Ratna	3	6.3	3
IET12351	IR50/IET7918	3	6.5	3
TNRH1	IR628294/IR10198-66-2 R	3	7.1	3
IR56382-17-3-2	IR28239-94/IR24632-34	5	7.5	3
IR58099-41-2-3	IR35366-90/IR324-29-47	5	7.5	3
IR57301-195-3-3	IR35293-125/IR32429-47	5	7.5	3
IR50	IR2153/IR28//IR36	5	7.6	3
RP1451-92-21-9	Rasi/Finegora	5	8.2	3
IET12428	IET5233/IR2153-26	5	8.8	3
BG850-2	BG380/BG367-4	5	8.9	3
IET12929	KAU8759	5	9.0	3
IR57311-95-2-3	IR39268-57/IR32429//IR42005-47	5	9.1	3
IET12891	Ratna/IR36	5	9.6	3
IET12402	Govind/Ranikajar	5	9.7	3
IR29725-117-2-3-3	IR19661-131/IR9125-209	5	9.8	3
IR53292-159-1-2-3	IR4563-52/IR31802-48	5	10.0	3
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	9	95.0	9

^aScored using 1-9 scale in SES. ^bScored using the methodology from the 1991 International Rice Tungro Nursery.

Pest resistance—insects

Resistance to whitebacked planthopper in wild and cultivated rices

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We evaluated wild rice species *Oryza officinalis*, *O. punctata*, and *O. latifolia* and genetically diverse rice varieties N22 (Wbph 1), ARC10239 (Wbph 1), Ptb33 (Wbph 3), Podwi A8 (Wbph 4), N'diang Marie (Wbph 5), IR2035-117-3 (Wbph 1 + Wbph 2), and Chaia Anaser (Wbph 1 + Wbph 3) for resistance to the white-

Damage ratings of selected wild and cultivated rices after infestation by WBPH nymphs in free-choice test.^a TNAU, Coimbatore, India.

Species/variety	IRRI accession number	Damage rating (d after infestation)		
		7	11	15
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101114	1.0 c	1.0 e	1.0 d
<i>O. punctata</i>	101439	1.0 c	1.0 e	1.4 d
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100963	1.0 c	1.0 e	1.0 d
<i>O. sativa</i>				
N22	4819	1.0 c	5.4 b	9.0 a
ARC10239	20803	1.0 c	3.4 c	9.0 a
Ptb33	19325	1.0 c	2.2 d	7.0 c
Podwi A8	15201	2.6 b	6.2 b	9.0 a
N'diang Marie	15859	1.0 c	3.4 c	8.2 b
IR2035-117-3	-	1.0 c	2.6 cde	7.4 bc
Chaia Anaser	16197	1.0 c	3.0 cd	7.8 bc
TN1		8.6 a	9.0 a	9.0 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Av of 5 replications.